

Effects of Religious Intolerance on the Economic Development of Nigeria: Islamic Panacea

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Abstract

One of the major obstacles to Nigeria's progress being a pluralistic country is intolerance. The inability to tolerate other people's religious practices, ideas and culture among others constitute the major reasons for religious crises and insecurity in the contemporary societies. This paper examined the effects of conflicts on economic development of Nigeria, as it highlights on the two major religions bodies (Islam and Christianity) that are used as the variables. These religions profess peace but there is rising conflicts that always result in violence among the adherents of the said religions and these remain constant feature of many Nigerians. The effects on the country's economic progress are very high. This paper aimed at elaborating the term "Religious Intolerance" in Islamic religious teachings, which recognizes what constitutes political, peace and economic growth of a society from Islamic perspectives through qualitative method and descriptive approach. The findings show that, the major causes of religious Intolerance in Nigeria are religious sentiment leading to bigotry and it has also led to reduction in economic activities. The work recommended among other things, that Religious leaders should be mobilized to preach tolerance and peaceful co-existence on the "NTA programme" nationwide and other means of information dissemination. Furthermore, the government should encourage the teaching of peace as a subject in Nigerian schools from primary to tertiary institutions. Then the nation can succeed in minimizing conflicts and attain the climax of economic growth.

Keywords: Intolerance, Religion, Islamic, Economics and Development

Introduction

One of the major challenges faced by human societies today, is the problem of intolerance among the adherents of different faiths. This country has continued to witness endemic destruction of lives and properties in contemporary times as a result of violence attribute to religion. This has become the headlines of many news items. And these attract people's attention, irrespective of their religious / political affiliations, geographical location and educational background. This phenomenon has become an international problem. Its momentum is fueled by the role it plays in the area of world religious struggle. It sometimes becomes the means through which some political groups attempt to achieve their objectives and obtain power. It has a great predicament in any human society, and most times, it is unpredictable. In fact, history shows that conflict is inevitable in any human relations and may occur within and among groups and communities.

There have been reprisal attacks on the northerners living in other parts of the country, as a result of incorrigible carnage and killings of people from other part of the country by their kin. These conflicts erupting from one place to another result into internal or inter-ethnic conflict among the citizens of the same country and thereby result in loss of lives and properties, displacement of people from their homes, closure of schools and disruption of commercial activities. Many countries have fallen prey to some forms of violence as a result of religious intolerance. The major cause of violence in Nigeria today seems to be religion. As Yinka noted most of the civil wars in world histories, particularly from 1945 to 1960 are ethnic and religious, and from 1960 to 1990 it increased to about three quarter and is continually increasing¹. Religion that had serves as tool for social transformations, harmony and development in many societies, has also on the other hand, being used as a motivation for violence. This made it arguable in some literatures that it is a "Double-edged Sword."² From time

immemorial Religious intolerance has adverse effects, as far as development of any society is concerned. It has become a useful tool to ferment political upheavals and socio-economic problem, using religion as camouflages. In the words of Max Weber as quoted by Giddens: ... each major religion of the world has developed its distinctive orientation towards all aspects of social life.... These differences have had profound consequences for the development of human society.³

Religion is a cultural phenomenon which has played dominant role in the socio-political/economic of man throughout the course of history. As an institution, it has served to meet certain needs within the society. It is within the context of the destructive use of religion in the history of several nations that the paper focuses on Islamic solution to economic situation of Nigeria. In the past two decades, religious intolerance has been at the centre of most violent conflicts around the world, thereby gaining notoriety as one of the prime security challenges confronting the world in the wake of the Cold War⁴. Without doubt, the greatest threat to economic development in Nigeria has always been religious intolerance. Nigeria is a country where Christianity and Islam enjoy large fellowship. As such, the country has been divided into two religious camps. It is often claimed that Nigeria has about 220 million people and about 80-85 Nigerians are identified as Muslims 55% are Muslims while the remaining percentage are either Christians or traditionalists.⁵

This study is diagnosing the causes of religious intolerance concludes by recommending ways of its reduction of such ugly situation. It also recommends the adoption of best-practices such as anti-corruption policies among the political elite and the masses. Religious intolerance on the other hand ignores the historical legacies as adopted by the contemporary religious and political institutions that are maintaining systems of bad governance.

Conceptual Clarifications

Religion: There is no acceptable definition of religion, as each and every Scholars of Religion try to frame the definitions and have been in one way or another has deficiency over the years. According to Adeniyi, Religion is the consciousness of one's dependence on transcendent being and the tendency to worship Him.⁶ He believes that religion is a means by which man is subordinated to the transcendent Being. Peter on the other hand defined religion as a system of symbols which act to establish powerful, pervasive and long-lasting moods and motivations in men by formulating conceptions of a general order of existence and clothing these conceptions with such an aura of factuality that the moods and motivations seems uniquely realistic.⁷ T. Omoregbe, sees religion as essentially a relationship, a link established between two persons namely a human person and a divine person believed to exist. That means, religion is man's relationship with the supernatural.⁸ In the same vein, there is an interaction between religion and the society within which it functions. Religion performs a variety of functions. The first is on the individual as it affects social behavior. The second is that religion interacts and influences the other facets or social institutions in the society, namely, Polity and economy. These institutions also influence the religious institutions, the effect of which affect in a fundamental way, a people's way of life.⁹

Intolerance: the word intolerance comes from two Latin words in and *tolerantem* in-meaning "not" and *tolerantem* meaning "to bear, endure". Religious Intolerance, therefore, means not being able to bear or endure beliefs of other people different from one's own. According to Encarta (2009), it is the act of refusing to accept differences; displaying an unwillingness or refusal to accept people who are different from you in views, beliefs, or lifestyles¹⁰. The intolerant person has difficulty accepting different views, beliefs, and practices of other people because of a lack of openness to experience and feelings of fear and uncertainty.

Religious Intolerance: Religious is the active of the word Religion while intolerance is a blind refusal to understand and respect views or positions that are opposed to one's cherished religious views. According to Ekwunife, religious intolerance is a blind and fixated mental and psychological negative attitude towards religious beliefs and practices that are contrary to one's cherished beliefs and practices.¹¹ The negative attitudes exhibit towards other peoples believes extends whereby leaders or groups in any society blindly refuse to respect contrary religious views and practices from others, except the ones they consider to be true. This religious intolerance

always results to series of violence and destruction as experienced in Nigeria during the past two decades. “Religious intolerance involved “hostility towards other religions, as well as the inability of religious adherents to harmonize between the theories and the practical aspect of religion.”¹² It is also a product of bigotry, which is the obstinate and intolerant devotion to one’s opinions and prejudices, especially the exhibition of intolerance and animosity toward persons of differing beliefs.¹³ The major reason for the violent conflict is largely due for lack of tolerance among the followers of different religions.

Development: *Cambridge Dictionary* defines, development as the process in which someone or something grows or changes and become more advanced. It further defined it as a process of developing something new.¹⁴ It further defined development as the process of economic and social transformation that is based on complex cultural and environmental factors and their interactions.¹⁵ Barder on the other hands defines development as “bringing social changes that allows people to achieve their human potentials”¹⁶. It conveys something about the capacity of economic, potential and social systems in providing the conducive environment for well-being on a sustainable long-term basis. Through this process the society will grow in wealth acquisition, mental enrichment and provide better living conditions of all the people. The society uses a combination of social, economic and institutional process as the means to acquire better living conditions.

Religious Intolerance and Its Effects in Nigeria

Nigeria is a multi-ethnic nation, blessed with three major religious bodies, namely; African Indigenous Religion, Christianity and Islam. Among the adherents of different religions in Nigeria, there are different levels and forms of religious conflicts. This is especially as a result of intolerance existing among the two major religious groups that is Christians and Muslims. These include intra or inter-religious conflicts. Intra-religious conflict often exists within the adherents of a particular religion like Maitatsine riot of 1980 in Kano and Izala versus Tijjaniyya brotherhood in Gombe in 1987. Religious intolerance involves denying the right of people of another religious faith to practice and express their beliefs freely. Religious intolerance is expressed in discrimination, repression and religious rivalry, and results in or results from persecution. It leads to war and persistent hatred between nations and between peoples within nations.

Some Causes of Religious Intolerance in Nigeria

Many religious wars were fought in the past. Even today a lot of conflicts and disturbances arise in society because of the religious reasons. The main causes of religious intolerance are as listed and explained below

Political: Politics is one of the major causes of intolerance among adherents of different religious body or within, where people get attracted towards politics and they started believing that their particular religion is the best and supreme, and therefore, became sentimental, through which their policies favour themselves, this creates misunderstanding and because of that, conflicts arose in the society and sometimes it became worst to handle. Okereke in Uchendu; ... these religious conflicts are, however, felt all over the country especially in the Eastern region where it gives way to different misconceptions about Muslims and Islam.¹⁷

Plurality of Religions: The plurality of ways by which human beings express their spiritual cravings is a reality. This fact points in a way to the view that human beings are by nature religious and that they differed and would continue to differ in religions. As regards the first assertion of man being by nature religious, this is in line with the anthropological fact that no human society has been found without one form of religion or another.¹⁸ Since the existence of plurality of religions is a reality, then there is bound to be religious intolerance. In fact, many religiously pluralistic societies all over the world have had to grapple with the problem of religious intolerance. Like most plural state, Nigeria is a country with religious diversity. African traditional religion, Christianity and Islam constitute the dominant religions in Nigeria, with each enjoying large followership. Aside from these major religions, there are other faiths like the Olumba Olumba, Eckankar, Bahai faith, Sat Guru Maharaji and of course, the beliefs that claim secular humanism. Intolerance among different religious adherents has become veracious

and alarming during the past two decades. This is more pronounced between the Christians and Muslims, with obvious negative effects on peaceful co-existence and interreligious relations.

Superiority Complex: Religious intolerance also ensues when one religion is perceived to be superior to the others. This is an inability of the adherents of different religious bodies or sect to acknowledge, accommodate and accept the rights of others as a result of their self-esteem. Invariably, such attitude is connected to the conviction that one's religion or sect is the only divinely ordained path to spiritual enlightenment and immortality in heaven. Consequently, a religious fanatic believes strongly that his religion or sect is unquestionably superior to others. If such zeal is wrongly channeled, it becomes dangerous for the life of the community and as it results into human fight abuse at the long run.

Aggravating Modes of Worship: One other trigger of religious intolerance that causes violence in Nigeria is the obstructive, disruptive and annoying modes of worship employed by the two dominant religions. There is a popular Christian tradition of organising mass crusades and revivals on public high ways or properties adjoining the high ways. Most of these crusades and revivals have the disrepute of obstructing vehicular and human movement for long periods of time in absolute disregard to tortuous and criminal liabilities.¹⁹ Many road users of other faiths – and even those of the same faith—see this practice as an affront to their legal rights to the use of public roads as well as a demonstration of religious arrogance and insensitivity. In the same vein, it has become an unwritten law for all public roads in Muslim-dominated areas to be blocked during Juma'at (Friday) prayers. Accordingly, all intending road users needing access through these roads on Fridays have often had the misfortune of abating their movements and waiting for the completion of Juma'at prayers. This tradition has triggered religious disturbances, particularly in places with evenly distributed numbers of Christians and Muslims. The 2001 Jos religious violence was caused by a mêlée that erupted after a Christian woman insisted on having her right of way through a public highway which was barricaded by Muslim worshipers on a Friday. This is also applicable to the Christians during their various sermons on Sunday.

Philosophy of Tolerance from Islamic Perspectives

Islamic philosophy of tolerance is socially and religiously order from Allah for harmonious human relationships in any multi-religious and multicultural society. It is a fundamental truth that religiously pluralistic nation states can only experience positive change in national life in an ambience of genuine attitude of tolerance towards people across religious and socio-cultural divides in public sphere.

The primary principle in Islam is peace, this is derived from the name of the religion itself *Salam* which means 'Peace'. Islam emphasizes on peace in communication with all Muslim and non-Muslim people in a society, and encourages its adherents to avoid war and violence. The Qur'an places limits on the use of force. The Qur'an acknowledges the right of retribution but states "those who forgive the injury and make reconciliation will be rewarded by God." (Qur'an 42: 40). The following are the principles of peace as dictated in the Qur'an by Allah:

The first principle of peace in Islam is the acceptance of Islam being made optional. According to the Qur'an, people are free to accept the religion of their choice. Qur'an says:

لَا إِكْرَاهَ فِي الدِّينِ قَدْ تَبَيَّنَ الرُّشْدُ مِنَ الْغَيِّ هِ ي فَمَنْ يَكْفُرْ بِالطَّاغُوتِ وَيُؤْمِنْ بِهَا هِ لِلَّهِ قَدَّ اسْتَمْسَكَ بِالْعُرْوَةِ الْوُثْقَى لَا انْفِصَامَ لَهَا وَ هِ اللّ سَمِيعٌ عَلِيمٌ.
"Let there be no compulsion in religion: Truth stands out clear from error: whoever rejects evil and believes in Allah has grasped the most trustworthy handhold that never breaks. And God hears and knows all things." (Qur'an 2: 256)

In support of the above verse, Allah says:

قُلِ الْحَقُّ مِنْ رَبِّكُمْ فَمَنْ شَاءَ فَلْيُؤْمِنْ وَ مَنْ شَاءَ فَلْيُكْفُرْ .

"The truth is from your Lord, so whoever wills- let him believe; and whoever wills - let him disbelieve" (Qur'an 18:29). This is an indication that, the acceptance of religion or the truth is at ones will.

The message to non-Muslims is, "For you is your religion, and for me is my religion." (Qur'an 109: 6). These passages counsel tolerance and patience toward the people of other faiths. This principle can in many cases prevent atmosphere of intolerance and violence.

The second principle of peace, tolerance and a non-violent society is that, God invites people to peace:

وَاللّٰهُ يَدْعُوْا اِلَى دَارِ السَّلَامِ وَيَهْدِيْ مَنْ يَشَاءُ اِلَى صِرَاطٍ مُسْتَقِيْمٍ

“Allah invites to the Home of Peace, and guides whomever He wills to a straight path”. (Qur’an 10: 25) This emphasizes on peaceful coexistence as the primary law.

يا ايها الذين آمنوا ادخلوا في السلم كافة ولا تتبعوا خطوات الشيطان انه لكم عدو ومبين

The Qur'an invites people to peace and life, and regards war and violence as the evil way. (Qur’an 2: 208)

و ان جنحوا للسلم فاجنح لها وتوكل على الله انه هو السميع العليم

That means: But if they incline towards peace, then incline towards it, and put your trust in Allah. He is the Hearer, the Knower (Qur’an 8: 61). The Qur'an commands that if your enemies desire peace, welcome it.

Islam permits defensive jihad on a number of conditions:

1. The occurrence of aggression Allah says,

وَقَاتِلُوا فِي سَبِيلِ اللّٰهِ الَّذِيْنَ يُقَاتِلُوْنَكُمْ وَلَا تَعْتَدُوا اِنَّ اللّٰهَ لَا يُحِبُّ الْمُعْتَدِيْنَ.

‘And fight in the cause of Allah those who fight you, but do not commit aggression; Allah does not love the aggressors’ (Qur’an 2: 190).

2. Aggression is unlawful but defense is permissible under certain circumstances. Allah says;

فَمَنْ اَعْتَدَى عَلَيْكُمْ فَاَعْتَدُوا عَلَيْهِ بِمِثْلِ مَا اَعْتَدَى عَلَيْكُمْ وَاَتَوْا اللّٰهَ وَاَعْلَمُوا اَنَّ اللّٰهَ مَعَ الْمُتَّقِيْنَ

“Whoever commits aggression against you, retaliate against him in the same measure as he has committed against you. And be conscious of Allah, and know that Allah is with the righteous” (Qur’an 2:194)

3. Observe the necessity, Allah says,

وَقَاتِلُوهُمْ حَتّٰى لَا تَكُوْنَ فِتْنَةً وَيَكُوْنَ الدّٰهِنُ لِلّٰهِ اِنَّ اَنْتُمْ لَعَدُوْنَا اِلَّا عَلَى الظّٰلِمِيْنَ

“And fight them until there is no oppression, and worship becomes devoted to Allah alone. But if they cease, then let there be no hostility except against the oppressors” (Qur’an 2:193).

4. For peace to reign in the society, Allah Prohibits insulting other peoples deity.

وَلَا تَسُبُّوا الَّذِيْنَ يَدْعُوْنَ مِنْ دُوْنِ اللّٰهِ فَيَسُبُّوا اللّٰهَ عَدُوًّا بِغَيْرِ عِلْمٍ كَذٰلِكَ زَيْنًا لِّكَ هَلْ اُمَّةٌ . عَمَلُهُمْ ثُمَّ اِلَى رَبِّهِمْ مَرْجِعُهُمْ فَيُنَبِّئُهُمْ بِمَا كَانُوْا يَعْمَلُوْنَ

“Do not insult those they call upon besides Allah, lest they insult Allah out of hostility and ignorance. We made attractive to every community their deeds. Then to their Lord is their return, and He will inform them of what they used to do” (Qur’an 6:108).

The third principle in creating a culture of peace and a non-violent society is to pay attention to the spiritual self-awareness inherent in our human nature that can move people away from violence. Human nature has a tendency for peace and friendship. Enjoying compassion, and love for others is part of our human nature. Violence is not our nature. Basically, non-violent relationships can bring us closer to our nature and help us connect and return to what is truly an acceptable way of life, one who contributes to one another's well-being and comfort. Human nature tends to peace, and not violence; violence comes as a result of how we react to situation, and not human nature.

Effects of Religious Intolerance on the Economic Development of Nigeria

This paper focuses on the effects of religious intolerance on the economic development of Nigeria. The most important issue as far as Nigeria is concern today, is how to find lasting solutions to ever increasing rates of religious intolerance that have been a clog in the wheel of progress in all spheres of human endeavours. The constant religious crises between the two major religions in Nigeria (Christianity and Islam), have resulted into dwindled economic fortune. In fact, these incessant conflicts have to a large extent ridicule Nigeria in the international communities, as no individuals or corporate body would want to invest in where security and safety of their investment is not guaranteed.

Findings

The impact of corruption on governance depends on the behaviour of politicians and public officials.

1. Religious bigotry / sentiments has deeply rooted in the mind of Nigerians, people are so emotional about them. These are detrimental to the ideas that could be vital and play significant role in the policy making that brought about development of a country' economy.
2. Religious intolerance is significant, it discourage the economic engagement of individuals. As a Instead of participating in elections and trusting political institutions, individuals can show *incivisme*, a French term for individual attitudes and activities that reject the idea that people ought to engage in politics.

Recommendations

This paper therefore, recommends that, for the realization of a society free of violence and in order to usher in the culture of religious tolerance / harmony and ensure peaceful co-existence:

1. The government should encourage the teaching of peace as a subject in Nigerian schools from primary to tertiary institutions;
2. Religious tolerance and peaceful co-existence should be held on the "NTA programme" nationwide and the other chanel which information could be disseminated nationwide;
3. To avoid conflicts and violence in societies, cultural and religious pluralism should be accepted, interactions and friendships between people with different religions should be pursued, on one hand, and to reject exclusivism and conflicts on the other hand;
4. Finally, religious leaders must encourage sincere and unpretentious inter-faith dialogue to reevaluate basic social issues as a way of promoting genuine attitude of tolerance.

Conclusion

Religious intolerance is one of the major factors impeding the economic growth of Nigeria. Islam is a religion of peace that plays a crucial role to secure peace among the inhabitant in the world, it is obvious that, almost every war or insurgency within a nation has involved in wrong religious perception; we therefore, strongly need to have a true interpretation of religious teachings as no religion teaches intolerance but peace. The Islamic teachings attempt to invite people to global peace and a peaceful life on the basis of theism, justice and piety. So, in Islam peace is an immortal and primary law. Lo! Allah loveth not aggressors." (Qur'an 2: 190). This interpretation of peace which is based on Qur'anic teachings can develop a widespread peace around the world and terminate conflicts in many places. "Invite (all) to the way of your Lord with wisdom and beautiful preaching; and argue with them in ways that are best and most gracious: for your Lord knows best who has strayed from His path, and who receives guidance." (Qur'an 16: 125).

Islamic teachings provide foundation for peaceful society in the following ways; first, the acceptance of Islamic faith is optional and not compulsory. Second; Islam emphasises on peace and non-violence society as its primary law. Third; the principle of paying attention to the spiritual self-awareness inherent in our human nature that can move people away from violence. However, In spite of these principles of peace in Islamic cultural heritage, Islamic teachings are misunderstood and misinterpreted by some of the adherents of Islam, so the responsibility lies on the intellectuals to use the possible means such as media to enlighten people to have better understanding of their faith in social aspects.

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